

Studies on Ascorbigen

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It was observed quite a long time back that certain vegetable materials gave a higher value for ascorbic acid, as estimated by titration with 2,6-dichlorophenol indophenol, when they were heated for a short period with water¹. These increased values were observed particularly in the cases of turnips, carrots, beets, potatoes, cauliflower and cabbage. The explanation offered was that some ascorbic acid was present in these foodstuffs in a bound form, from which it was released by hydrolysis.

Guha and Pal² confirmed these results in regard to cabbage and a few other plant materials and termed the bound ascorbic acid as "ascorbigen" for brevity. Some workers³⁻⁵ were of the opinion, however, that the observed increase in ascorbic acid value on heating with water was due to the thermal destruction of ascorbic acid oxidase present in these plant materials, which normally oxidises ascorbic acid when the material is crushed, thus giving low values of ascorbic acid. Pal and Guha⁶, however, provided considerable evidence to indicate the existence of ascorbigen. They prepared absolute alcohol extracts of cabbage after macerating it with anhydrous sodium sulphate and found that on heating the extracts on a boiling water bath the indophenol-reducing value was considerably increased. They found that ascorbigen was quite labile and would release ascorbic acid at the pH of gastric juice. They, however, found that all vegetables and fruits did not contain ascorbigen but the *Brassica* group of vegetables contained considerable quantities of this substance. This work was further extended by Sen Gupta and Guha⁷ and it was observed that among the different solvents used for extracting ascorbigen from dried cabbage, chloroform was the most efficient. The extracts were found free from ascorbic acid and dehydro-ascorbic acid. The aqueous solutions of the dried chloroform extracts, when heated on a water-bath for 10 minutes in an atmosphere of nitrogen, produced a considerable quantity of indophenol-reducing substance or substances. Chloroform would not extract ascorbic acid oxidase and the extract also did not show its presence on treatment with ascorbic acid. The value of the reducing substances obtained on heating the chloroform extract could not therefore be in anyway connected with the thermal inactivation of ascorbic acid oxidase. It was further observed that 60-70% of the reducing substances, produced by heating the aqueous solutions of the dried chloroform extract, disappeared when these were treated with an ascorbic acid oxidase preparation from cucumber. This would indicate that 60-70% of the reducing substances represent ascorbic acid; the rest apparently represents some non-specific reducing substances. Biological experiments with scorbutic guinea pigs showed that the chloroform extracts, which were free from ascorbic acid, were active and their activities were roughly comparable with equivalent amounts of pure ascorbic acid. Exact correspondence could not be expected as about 30% of the reducing substances produced from chloroform extracts by heat appeared to be non-specific. Sen

Gupta, Sarkar and Guha⁸ confirmed these results by carrying out biological experiments by using the histological tooth method in which the degree of protection to predentine given by ascorbic acid was measured.

Ghosh and Guha⁹ carried out a series of experiments for concentrating ascorbigen from cabbage juice. Protein precipitating reagents did not precipitate ascorbigen. It was observed, however, that norite 'charcoal' and active 'charcoal' would adsorb 60% of the ascorbigen from fresh cabbage juice. It was possible to elute the larger fraction of ascorbigen from this adsorbate by gently heating it with 70:30 chloroform-alcohol mixture. The extract was evaporated in a vacuum desiccator and it was taken up with the minimum quantity of water and centrifuged. The centrifugate was evaporated to dryness in vacuum and on heating its aqueous solution it was found to release indophenol-reducing substances, 60% of which was oxidised by ascorbic acid oxidase. The rest apparently represented non-specific reducing substances. The ascorbigen preparation could be further concentrated by means of sodium tungstate. The active preparations gave positive tests for carbohydrates and negative tests for proteins. The materials, however, were obviously still impure.

McHenry and Reedman¹⁰ carried out chemical, spectrophotographic, and biological experiments with potato. They obtained similar evidence for the presence of the bound form of ascorbic acid in potato.

This problem was not much pursued, however, during the war years, but interest in the subject revived after the war, particularly in the Soviet Union and Czechoslovakia. Sumstov¹¹ and Terent'eva¹² substantially confirmed the results obtained by Guha and co-workers. They also obtained active extracts from cabbage juice by the charcoal absorption method and they also demonstrated the biological activity of their ascorbigen preparation by experiments with guinea pigs.

Striking advances in the subject were made in post-war years by Prochazka and his co-workers¹³. They identified the presence of ascorbic acid in the hydrolyzate of a preparation of ascorbigen by paper chromatography. On paper chromatogram the ascorbic acid released from ascorbigen showed the same R_f value as that of pure ascorbic acid. Prochazka *et al.*¹⁴ have reported the isolation of pure ascorbigen from cabbage (yield about 5 mg. per kg. of cabbage) and they have given it the empirical formula $C_{17}H_{17}O_7N$. Its melting point was reported to be 86-89°. Although it was amorphous, it was said to give crystalline derivatives with picric acid and diazomethane. They considered that the ascorbigen molecule consisted of ascorbic acid and an indole moiety, as hydrolysis of the substance yielded ascorbic acid and another component giving the Ehrlich test for indoles. Since then Prochazka and Severa¹⁵ have described an improved process for the isolation of ascorbigen.

This investigation was resumed in recent years in this laboratory. Malakar and Guha¹⁶ have isolated a material from cabbage juice whose empirical formula agrees with that for ascorbigen given by Prochazka *et al.*^{14,15} and its melting point is 84°. It also splits into ascorbic acid and an indole moiety giving the Ehrlich reaction. Its absorption spectra also agree with those given by Prochazka *et al.*¹⁵.

The method consists of adsorbing ascorbigen of cabbage juice with active carbon, eluting it with a mixture of chloroform and rectified spirit (7:3), concentrating the extract *in vacuo* and subjecting it to chromatography in a silica gel column, and fractionating the

active material by gradient elution with ethyl acetate and chloroform. The richest fraction yielded a white amorphous substance which gave on hydrolysis 50% of its weight as ascorbic acid.

The ascorbigen so isolated has been investigated chromatographically both before and after hydrolysis by Bose and Guha¹⁷ and ascorbic acid and an indole compound as moieties of the ascorbigen molecule have been confirmed. Bose and Guha¹⁷ have also shown the presence of ascorbigen by the chromatographic procedure not only in *Cruciferae*, of which the *Brassica* group contains a considerable quantity of it, but also in certain non-cruciferous plants, particularly chillies and bitter gourd.

The biological role of ascorbigen in plants is under investigation both in Prague¹⁸ (Kutacek *et al.*) and in this laboratory. Preliminary experiments indicate its rise and fall at different stages of growth and flowering, which might be related to its requirement or otherwise at different stages of metabolism.

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